

***THE CONCEPT OF MEDIADISKURS AND THE RESULTS OF PRACTICE IN
ENGLISH AND UZBEK***

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Abstract. This article will consider specific issues of adequacy when translating artistic means from Uzbek to English and vice versa. He also studies the potential patterns of these problems with an emphasis on improving the accuracy and efficiency of translations of artistic media. Difficulties in translating artistic instruments from Uzbek to English. The translation of the means of art from Uzbek into English presents several difficulties that arise due to linguistic, technical and cultural differences between the two languages.

Keywords: technical English, teaching English in universities and colleges, mediums, terminology.

One of the main problems is the lack of equivalent terms for certain artistic means in both languages. For example, Uzbek may have specific terms for traditional art objects that do not have a direct equivalent in English, and vice versa. This can lead to ambiguities and misunderstandings in the translation process. Another difficulty is the technical nature of artistic mediums, which often require clear and specific terminology. The correct translation of the terms requires in-depth knowledge of both source and instructive languages, as well as comprehensive knowledge of the technical aspects of artistic means. These inexperienced translators may have difficulty properly conveying the intended meaning of the terms of the artistic medium. Cultural differences also play a large role in translating artistic media. Some artistic mediums may have different cultural meanings in Uzbek and English-speaking contexts, which may affect their translation. For example, a particular art medium may have significant cultural or historical significance in Uzbek culture, but this may not be fully expressed in its English translation. Moreover, the lack of standardized terminology for artistic means in both languages can lead to inconsistencies and confusion in their translation. Different translators may use different terms for the same artistic medium, leading to a lack of homogeneity in translation materials.

When translating artistic media from Uzbek to English, several yyechim can be implemented to solve issues of adequacy. First of all, it is very important to attract translators who have a deep knowledge of both languages and cultures, as well as experience in the technical aspects of artistic means. Translators with such skill levels are able to accurately

capture the subtleties and complexities of artistic medium terms, ensuring that their translations are both accurate and culturally sensitive. In addition, the development of standardized terminology for artistic means in Uzbek and English will help to improve the consistency and accuracy of their translation. This can be achieved by collaborating between language professionals, artists and teachers of both cultures to create a common set of terms for artistic media. In addition, the provision of contextual and cultural information along with translated materials will help to eliminate the discrepancy between the Uzbek and English-speaking audience. This helps to ensure that the cultural significance of certain artistic media is fully expressed in their translations. Finally, the research and collaboration between translators, artists and teachers of both cultures helps to identify and solve certain translation problems related to artistic means. This can lead to the development of advanced experiments in translating artistic media from Uzbek to English, ultimately increasing the adequacy and efficiency of their translations.

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